

6. V. BALIAH and P. SUBBARAYAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1833.
7. N. D. DAWSON and A. BURGER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 207.
8. F. CHALLENGER and J. F. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2675.
9. W. STRECKER and C. GROSSMANN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1916, **94**, 74.
10. J. R. VAUGHAN and D. S. TARBELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 144.
11. F. CHALLENGER and A. T. PETERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2616.
12. VON A. MICHAELIS, *Ann.*, 1902, **321**, 216.
13. VON A. MICHAELIS, *Ann.*, 1902, **321**, 201.
14. VON A. MICHAELIS, *Ann.*, 1902, **321**, 204.
15. F. F. BLICKE and S. R. SAFIR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 575.
16. VON A. MICHAELIS and E. PACTOW, *Ann.*, 1886, **233**, 73.
17. F. F. BLICKE and E. L. CATALINE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 422.
18. VON A. MICHAELIS and L. WITZ, *Chem. Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 49.
19. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Wiley, New York, 1958, p. 65.

Reaction of Lead(IV) Acetate with Steroidal Semicarbazones

SHAFIULLAH* and SHAHID A. ANSARI

Steroid Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry,
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002

Manuscript received 11 July 1989, accepted 6 December 1989

In recent past, great interest has been shown on the reaction of lead(IV) acetate with steroidal oximes¹, epoxides² and nitroolefins^{3,4}. It has also been reported⁵ that the semicarbazones on oxidation with LTA give the corresponding oxadiazolinone. In view of these observations we carried out the reaction of some easily accessible steroidal semicarbazones with lead(IV) acetate under the conditions reported in the literature. It is pertinent to mention that in these cases the expected oxadiazolinones were not isolated. The structures of the compounds have been established on the basis of spectral evidence, comparison with authentic samples and chemical transformation wherever possible. The stereochemical study has been done by ¹H nmr spectroscopy.

5 α -Cholestan-6-one semicarbazone (**1**) in dichloromethane when treated with lead(IV) acetate

furnished 5 α -cholestan-6-one (**4**) and 5 α -acetoxycholestan-6-one (**7**). The ir spectrum of compound **7** exhibited bands at 1745 (CH₃COO), 1720 (C=O), 1240 and 1220 cm⁻¹ (C-O axial acetate)⁶. The ¹H nmr spectrum showed a singlet at δ 2.02 for three acetate protons. Under similar reaction conditions 3 β -chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one semicarbazones (**2**) furnished 3 β -chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one (**5**) and 3 β -chloro-7 α -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (**8**). The ir spectrum of **8** showed bands at 1740 (CH₃COO), 1720 (C=O), 1235 and 1220 cm⁻¹ (C-O). The ¹H nmr spectrum displayed a singlet at δ 2.1 (CH₃COO) and a broad singlet at δ 5.35 integrating for one proton assigned to C7-proton. Drieding model revealed that the dihedral angle between the plane of C8- β -H (axial) and C7- β -H was almost 90° which may account for the C7- β -H appearing as a broad singlet. Therefore, the acetoxy group at C7 is axially (α) oriented. Similarly, 3 β -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one semicarbazone (**3**) yielded 3 β -hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (**6**) and 3 β -hydroxy-7 α -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (**9**). The ir and ¹H nmr spectral data of compound **9** were comparable to those of **8**.

Experimental

All m.ps. were observed on a Koflar apparatus, and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were obtained on a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A-60 D instrument with Me₄Si as the internal standard. Tlc plates were coated with silica gel and sprayed with an aqueous 20% perchloric acid solution. Light petroleum ether refers to a fraction having b.p. 60–80°.

Preparation of steroidal semicarbazones: To a solution of steroidal-6-ones (2.0 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was added a solution of a mixture of semicarbazide hydrochloride (2.0 g) and sodium acetate (3.0 g) in water (20 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h, cooled and the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from methanol.

General procedure: LTA (2.0 g) was added in one portion to a stirred suspension of 5 α -cholestan-6-one semicarbazone, m.p. 210° (**1**, 2.0 g) in dry dichloromethane (50 ml) at 0°. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 3 h at room temperature and then treated with 2.4 N HCl (5.0 ml). The contents were poured in ice-cooled water and extracted with dichloromethane. The organic layer was washed with water and sodium bicarbonate solution (20%) and evaporated. The oily residue thus obtained was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g) column. Elution with light petroleum ether-ether (40:1) gave a solid which was recrystallised from methanol to give 5 α -cholestan-6-one (**4**; 0.85 g, 42.5%), m.p. and m.m.p. 97° (lit.⁷ 98°). Further elution with petroleum ether-ether (35:1) furnished 5 α -acetoxycholestan-6-one (**7**; 0.70 g, 35%), which was recrystallised from methanol, m.p.

81° (Found: C, 78.30; H, 10.86. $C_{29}H_{48}O_8$ requires: C, 78.32; H, 10.87%); ν_{max} 1 745 (CH_3COO), 1 720 ($C=O$), 1 240 and 1 220 cm^{-1} ($C-O$); δ 2.02 (s, $C5-\alpha-O-COCH_3$), 1.2 ($ClO-CH_3$), 0.73 ($C13CH_3$), 0.93 and 0.83 (other CH_3).

Under similar reaction conditions, 3 β -chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one semicarbazone (2; 2.0 g, m.p. 152°) furnished 3 β -chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one (5; 0.75 g, 37.5%) on elution with petroleum ether-ether (30:1) which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 128° (lit.⁸ 129°). Further elution with petroleum ether-ether (28:1) yielded 3 β -chloro-7 α -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (8; 0.65 g, 32.5%), which failed to crystallise (Found: C, 72.68; H, 9.87. $C_{29}H_{47}ClO_8$ requires: C, 72.69; H, 9.88%); give positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 1 740 (CH_3COO), 1 715 ($C=O$), 1 235, 1 210 cm^{-1} ($C-O$) and 710 cm^{-1} ($C-Cl$); δ 5.35 (br s, C7- β H), 4.23 (m, $W_{1/2}$ 16 Hz, C3- α H), 2.00 (s, C7- $\alpha-O-COCH_3$), 1.18 ($ClO-CH_3$), 0.70 ($C13-CH_3$), 0.90 and 0.79 (other CH_3).

3 β -Acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one semicarbazone (3; m.p. 222°) under identical procedure conditions gave an oily residue which was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with light petroleum ether-ether (15:1) gave 3 β -hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (6; 0.65 g, 32.5%) which was crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 143° (lit.⁹ 142–43°). Further elution with petroleum ether-ether (10:1) furnished 3 β -hydroxy-7 α -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (9; 0.70 g, 40%), which was recrystallised from acetone 125° (Found: C, 75.58; H, 10.49. $C_{29}H_{48}O_4$ requires: C, 75.60; H, 10.50%); ν_{max} 3 450 (OH), 1 740 (CH_3COO), 1 720 ($C=O$), 1 230 and 1 215 cm^{-1} ($C-O$); δ 5.24 (br s C7- β H), 4.46 (m, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3- α H), 2.5 (s, C3- β OH) 2.2 (s, C7- $\alpha-O-COCH_3$), 1.6 ($ClO-CH_3$), 0.75 ($C13-CH_3$), 0.92 and 0.80 (other CH_3). This on treatment with Ac_2O/Py gave the diacetate (10) as an oil (lit.¹⁰ oil).

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. S. A. A. Zaidi, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, for facilities and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

- SHAFIULLAH and H. ALI, *Syntheses*, 1979, 124.
- SHAFIULLAH and R. K. PATHAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 292.
- S. HUSAIN, V. AGARWAL and K. C. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, 27, 852.
- SHAFIULLAH, S. HUSAIN and D. M. BASHA, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1983, 114, 121.
- J. P. ANTHONY and J. WARKENTIN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, 57, 2681.
- L. J. BELLAMY, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Wiley, New York, 1958, p. 189.
- C. W. SHOPPER, D. N. JONES, J. R. LEWIS and G. H. R. SUMMERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2876.
- A. WINDAUS and O. DALMER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1919, 52, 162.
- A. WINDAUS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3752.
- SHAFIULLAH, H. ALI and SHAMSUZZAMAN, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1981, 107, 97.

Studies in Spiro-heterocycles. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activities of some New Spiro(indolin-3,5'-pyrazolin)-1'-phenyl-2-ones and Spiro(indolin-3,5'-isoxazolin)-2-ones.

M. D. ANKHIWALA

Department of Chemistry, R. R. Mehta College of Science
Palanpur-385 002

Manuscript received 28 April 1989, revised 6 September 1989
accepted 4 January 1990

VARIOUS indole derivatives show varied biological activities¹. If the indole ring is joined to other heterocyclic systems through a spiro-carbon atom the resulting compounds show an increased spectrum of biological activities. Spiro-indoline-pyrazolines² and spiro-indoline-isoxazoline³ possess a wide range of biological activities.

Keeping the above observations in view, various spiro-pyrazolines and spiro-isoxazolines have been synthesised and screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities. 2-Hydroxyacetophenone derivatives (2) were prepared by the literature method⁴. Reaction of indolin-2,3-dione(isatin) (1) with 2-hydroxyacetophenone derivatives (2) in presence of diethylamine or piperidine base gave 3-hydroxy-3-phenacylindolin-2-ones (3)⁵. Dehydration of 3 by dilute hydrochloric acid or by hydrochloric acid in the presence of acetic acid gave 3-phenacylidene indoline-2-ones (4)⁵. Cyclocondensation of α,β -unsaturated ketone (4) with phenylhydrazine in equimolar amount in the presence of ethanol gave spiro-(indolin-3,5'-pyrazolin)-1'-phenyl-2-ones (5)⁶. Further, cyclocondensation of 4 with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in equimolar amount in the presence of ethanolic alkali gave spiro-(indolin-3,5'-isoxazolin)-2-ones (6)⁵ (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds have been supported by elemental, ir and pmr spectral analysis.

In compounds 5, ir bands have been observed in the regions 3 400–3 300 (OH), 3 100–2 800 (CH_2 , arom. and aliph.), 1 725–1 700 ($C=O$), 1 650–1 600 ($C=N$) and 1 240–1 220 cm^{-1} ($C-N$). In pmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of 5a, signals have been observed at δ 2.4 (s, CH_3) and 7.3–6.9 (m, ArH). In compounds 6, ir bands have been observed in the regions 1 730–1 700 ($C=O$) and 1 660–1 600 cm^{-1} ($C=N$). In pmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of 6a, signal have been observed at δ 2.6 (s, CH_3) and 7.5–6.8 (m, ArH).

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening of spiro-pyrazolines and spiro-isoxazolines were carried out using cup-plate⁶ method at a concentration of 50 $\mu g ml^{-1}$ using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Marcasane serratia* and fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

Most of the compounds showed activity against different strains of bacteria and fungi (7–21 mm, zone of inhibition). Most of the compounds were found to be active against gram-(+) bacteria and